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Ready to use sample management system

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Abstract:

This deliverable describes the implementation of SSHOC Deliverable 4.1, specifying "A sample management system for cross-national web survey". The deliverable, called WPSS, is a technical infrastructure aimed at supporting large-scale, high quality cross-national multi-language web surveys.

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Executive Summary

This document describes the output of Task 4.1 of the SSHOC (Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud) project funded by the European Commission under Grant Agreement N° 823782.

A technical infrastructure called Web Panel Sample Service (WPSS) has been implemented following the specifications published in November 2019 as *deliverable 4.1*¹ "A sample management system for cross-national web survey".

This WPSS technical infrastructure is aimed at supporting large-scale, high quality cross-national multi-language web surveys. It provides a centralised management of survey fielding orchestration (publishing surveys, sending survey invites and reminders, fieldwork monitoring), and a decentralised and privacy-compliant handling of panellists' data.

This document outlines the twofold infrastructure that has been implemented, a Python² / Django³ web application paired with a Qualtrics survey platform license. WPSS interacts through the API provided by Qualtrics⁴ to a dedicated and tailored Qualtrics License.

After presenting the user roles involved either in the study coordination, sample management, messages and questionnaire editors and translators, the document presents the platform (WPSS or Qualtrics) each role is granted access to, and the actions available.

Last, the document describes the relations between the 4.2 deliverable and the CRONOS-2 project led by ESS ERIC (funded by the European Commission under Grant Agreement ESS-SUSTAIN-2 N°871063); a WPSS instance dedicated to the first use case of the *D4.2 "a ready to use sample management system" deliverable*, the "Opinion survey for <country>" survey.

¹ Rory Fitzgerald, Gianmaria Bottoni, Curtis Jessop, Øyvind Straume, Quentin Agren, Geneviève Michaud, & Nicolas Sauger. (2019). SSHOC D4.1 A sample management system for cross-national web survey (V2.6). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4436727>

² Python programming language, doc. version used (as of 19/11/2021) <https://docs.python.org/3.9/>

³ Django web framework, doc. version used (as of 19/11/2021) <https://docs.djangoproject.com/en/2.2/>

⁴ Qualtrics API reference: <https://api.qualtrics.com/api-reference/ZG9jOjg0MDczOA-api-reference> (last consult. 19/11/2021)

Abbreviations and Acronyms

API	Application Programming interface
ARIA	Accessible Rich Internet Applications
CDSP	Center for socio-political data (Sciences Po, CNRS)
CRONOS	CROss-National Online Survey
DPO	Data Protection Officer
ESS-ERIC	European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure Consortium
EURISE	European Research Infrastructure Software Engineers' Network (CESSDA, CLARIN & DARIAH ERIC)
SMS	Short Message Service
WPSS	Web Panel Sample Service

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Introduction

This deliverable provides a description of a web application called Web Panel Sample Service (WPSS) dedicated for online comparative longitudinal surveys. The content uses and complements the companion website, available online at <https://cdsp-scpo.github.io/wpss-doc/>.

The Web Panel Sample Service has been specified and developed within the framework of SSHOC, as part of the Work Package *Innovations in data production*, led by ESS-ERIC. The software was conceived and developed by City, University of London and the CDSP's IT team at Sciences Po.

There is no shortage of existing web survey platforms. Generally, along with user-friendly questionnaire design tools, they allow users to manage lists of contacts to which surveys may be distributed through different communication channels.

However, for the fielding of cross-national high-quality surveys, major shortcomings remain. To overcome these, the task team focused on the following:

- **Layered access** to contact data: First, access to panellists' data should be confined to sample managers, and while it needs to be kept up to date, not all of it is appropriate to be shared with a third-party survey platform.
- **Fielding orchestration**: Second, survey orchestration should be handled centrally, but without detailed access to individual panelist data.
- **Flexible contact modes**: Third, contact modes with panelists not only must include both email and short text messages (SMS), but they should be possible to freely intertwine during fieldwork: for example, sending an email invite and an SMS reminder. This feature is either complex or missing on existing survey platforms.

The software

When implementing the specifications that were established by ESS ERIC and Sciences Po as D4.1, the team focused on keeping control over the technical stack (limiting the software dependencies), adopt a Docker container publication pipeline.

The team also looked for early feedback, to inform design and implementation decisions. As an example, this drove the team to transform a mandatory step (the connection to the panellist portal) into a fully optional step.

Producing a flexible and scalable infrastructure has been also a major concern, confirmed by the first use case (see [WPSS in use](#)). WPSS allows to add on the fly sample, sample managers, panellists, as well as languages. A sample can use one or more languages as well.

The ESS DPO has been consulted at different stages of the process. Her involvement has been essential to the final stage reached in terms of personal data protection.

A first proof of concept has been tested in April 2020, following releases in March 2021 and August 2021. These tests allowed the project team to collect valuable feedback, analysed during the team's weekly meetings.

A two-fold information system

The team conceived a two-fold information system, the WPSS web application and a Qualtrics license. The two components are coupled through the survey platform API.

Several user roles are defined. They are granted either access to the WPSS portal, or to the survey platform, as described in the figure below:

fig 1.: The WPSS information system structure, from WPSS companion website (<https://cdsp-scpo.github.io/wpss-doc/wpss/components/>)

User roles and actions

Actions (like distributing a survey, sending invites and reminders) are triggered from WPSS, and content (questionnaire creation, email and short text messages edition and translation) is managed from the survey platform. Access to personal data is granted on a need-to-know basis, for each role, as summarized in the table below:

role	WPSS account	Survey platform account	Access to personal data
Survey coordinator	✓		
Sample manager	✓		assigned sample data
Survey developer		✓	
Message editor		✓	
Content translator		✓	
Data archive		✓	pseudonymized survey data

fig 2.: WPSS users roles and rights from the WPSS companion website (<https://cdsp-scpo.github.io/wpss-doc/wpss/roles/>)

Study coordinator

Survey coordinators are part of the central study team and are responsible for a range of survey and fieldwork management tasks. Study coordinators are not able to access panel members' contact details. As part of the initial setup of the application, a set of study coordinator user accounts are created by the development team. From then on, the study coordinator is autonomous to invite sample managers to upload their sample contact data.

fig 3: the study coordinator landing page on WPSS

Sample managers

Sample managers accounts are created by survey coordinators. They are assigned one or more samples. They are responsible for keeping sample data accurate. Sample manager users may only perform actions and access contact data related to the sample/s they have been assigned to.

Content editors

Survey developers, Message editors and Content Translators, as content-related roles are exclusively granted access to the survey platform.

A message editor drafts emails and short text messages on the survey platform. The study coordinator then invites translation editors to include content translated in as many languages as used by the total study sample. Once translated and shared with WPSS, messages will be used by the study coordinator to invite panellists to a survey or to send reminders and follow-up messages as desired.

The WPSS information system can accommodate as many languages as needed. A language value is set at the respondent level, it is a mandatory value. This gives the system flexibility, for example to accommodate samples using several languages, or the same language to be shared by several samples.

Data archive staff

Data archive staff is the only role that is granted access to pseudonymized survey data on the survey platform.

WPSS in use, *the opinion survey for <country>*

Use cases for such a tool can be found in the field of the Social Sciences and Humanities but may extend to broader contexts as well. Many research fields can benefit from such a tool that allows a decentralized sample management in a multilingual setup for longitudinal studies.

Starting October 2021, a production ready release of the WPSS supports its first full-scale use case, within the frame of the European Social Survey for the follow-up web panel of the ESS round 10, Opinion Survey for <Country> also known as the CRONOS-2 project (funded by the H2020 program ESS-SUSTAIN-2 under grant agreement N°871063). The CRONOS 2 panel is composed of 6 waves (4 cross-national waves and 2 country-specific waves) which will be carried out in 12 European countries (UK, Iceland, France, Finland, Sweden, Czechia, Austria, Hungary, Portugal, Belgium, Slovenia, and Italy). Panellists will be recruited off the back of the European Social Survey Round 10 and invited to participate in six 20-minute long surveys, plus a Welcome survey. Panellists will be provided with an unconditional incentive of 5 euro/pound for each survey invitation they receive.

An instance of the WPSS has been set up and is currently in production at <https://opinionsurvey.org>.

The image shows a mobile-style login page for 'Opinion Study'. At the top, there is a red flower-like logo. Below it, the title 'Connexion' is displayed in a bold, dark font, followed by the subtitle 'Première connexion' in a smaller, blue font. The form contains two input fields: 'Email' and 'Mot de passe', both with red asterisks indicating they are required. Below the password field, there is a blue button labeled 'Connexion' and a link 'Utiliser le numéro de téléphone'. At the bottom of the form area, there is a link 'Mot de passe oublié ?'. The footer of the page includes the text 'Opinion Study', 'Powered by WPSS', and a version number 'v.F438636'.

fig 4: the "opinion study for <country>" WPSS localised login page

Several online training sessions have taken place, either aimed at study coordinators, sample managers or translation editors. The sessions have provided valuable feedback both for the documentation and for the development.

Package Contents

WPSS is a web application that could be used as a standalone⁵ sample management web tool, but to fully use its potential, it requires a tailored Qualtrics license, including specific options (directory, data isolation, data encryption, SMS, API). Given this dependency and costs implied, the team cannot offer access to a demo website.

The development team is reachable at itcdsp-scpolst@sciencespo.fr and welcomes requests to share, in addition to the companion website including detailed user guides publicly available at <https://cdsp-scpo.github.io/wpss-doc/>, the WPSS source code, and associated docker images. The team is also available to present the tool.

The WPSS source code and associated Docker image are available under GNU GPLv3.⁶

⁵ This has been addressed in D4.1, "Appendix 1: The functionalities of the SMS with survey platforms different from Qualtrics" <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4436727>

⁶ GNU General Public License version 3, <https://opensource.org/licenses/GPL-3.0>